

JUNE 20-22, 2019, OPLENAC, TOPOLA, SERBIA

THIRD JOINT MEETING OF NATIONAL PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETIES

In the organisation of a

SLOVAK AND SERBIAN PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETIES

**HEALTH RISK,
NUTRITION AND DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS:
OXIDATIVE STRESS AND POLYPHENOLS IN
THE HEART OF SERBIAN WINERIES**

FINAL PROGRAM & ABSTRACT BOOK

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SERBIAN PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETY

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EFFECTS OF TRAINING AND DETRAINING ON MUSCLE STRENGTH IN ROWERS

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Annual planning and periodization play a great role in muscle adaptation in rowers. Considering that the training's main effect is to increase specific muscle strength, while in detraining rowers work on general muscle strength and active recovery, the aim of the study was to compare strength of different muscle groups between periods of training and detraining. The study was conducted at the Department of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, and included 34 male and female rowers, 15 to 18 years of age. Muscle strength was measured using Concept2 DYNO dynamometer. Strength of the arm extensors and flexors as well as the leg extensors was measured twice, at the end of competition season (peak of performance) and before the start of competition season (after detraining). Significant difference was found in absolute strength, relative strength and contraction speed in arm flexors and extensors, as well as in relative strength and contraction speed in leg extensors between training and detraining period ($p < 0.05$). No difference was found in leg extensors relative strength between two measurements ($p > 0.05$). Periodization of the annual rowing training program has bigger impact on upper limbs adaptation oscillations compared with the lower limbs muscles in the terms of absolute strength.